

FAIR Software: Interactive Introduction

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Where are you joining us from today?

What is the position / job title in your e-mail signature?

Postdoc

RSE

senior software developer

Research Scientist

Software Engineering Group Leader

Full stack software developer

Community manager

Community Manager

Research Software Engineer

What is the position / job title in your e-mail signature?

PhD researcher

Team leader

Researcher

Community Manager

Professor

Research project officer

RSE

software engineer and metadata specialist

Director & Senior Research Fellow

What is the position / job title in your e-mail signature?

PhD student

Researcher

Software Development Scientist

Master student

Why did you choose to join this workshop?

learn about FAIR principles

Curious

Interesting topic

learn about the latest work in the working groups

Learn

Learn and share info about FAIR4RS

Hear about progress from the working group

interested in promoting software as part of the research process, interested in FAIR principles

contribute to the discussion on FAIR principles for research software

Why did you choose to join this workshop?

to connect with this community and hear the latest

learn more about FAIR4RS

Stared a PhD about open science (eco, eco). Want to learn more about open software

Learn and exchange thoughts on applying FAIR principles to research software.

Wanting to find out more and get feedback from RSE community

Learn more about FAIR and Research Software

learn and share

Learn about supporting researchers with FAIR practices

Institutional implementation interest

Why did you choose to join this workshop?

Recently started as RSE, reaching out internationally

Are you familiar with the FAIR data principles?

Recap: FAIR data principles

- Findable (metadata and data should be easy to find)
- Accessible (users need to know how they can be accessed)
- Interoperable (data needs to be integrated with other data, and interoperate with analysis code)
- Reusable (metadata and data should be well-described to facilitate reuse)
- See also <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

"(Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier." Which FAIR principle?

"(Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards." Which FAIR principle?

"(Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol." Which FAIR principle?

"(Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data." Which FAIR principle?

FAIR

Findable
Accessible
Interoperable
Reusable

2016: "The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship" (Wilkinson et al., doi:10.1038/sdata.2016.18)

2018: "Central to the realization of FAIR are **FAIR Digital Objects, which may represent data, software or other research resources.**" (European Commission)

But: **How do the FAIR Principles relate to software?**

Mismatch between the broad intentions of the **4 foundational FAIR principles** and how the **15 FAIR Guiding Principles** are communicated and perceived.

What is data?

group of information

information in a digital format

The plural of datum ;-)

Everything!

observations

life.

raw information

any useful/usable information

Digital representation of observations from the real world

What is data?

Information: images, values...

Sorted information

Any piece of symbolic representation associated to a referent in the real world

facts and observations

What is software?

Digital methods

Instructions that act on data

Series of instructions

data generator, but also itself data
(source code, artifacts)

Executable instructions/algorithm
using a programming language

Instructions for a machine to execute
a routine

Computer code

The implementation of functionality
that can be executed by a computer
on data.

programs/operations for a computer

What is software?

Any piece of work that executes something on a machine

Software can be data as well.
Documentation, Code as data

machine-readable instructions and knowledge

Programme which interpret, analyse information/data

translator for data into other data

Ensemble of computer executed function with a specific aim

packaged algorithms

What do data and software have in common?

digital

technical standards

Both can be a research outcome

Software use data to create more data

Source

Software can allow for the acquisition of data

metadata

useless without proper documentation

Need to be well documented

What do data and software have in common?

Both can have multiple versions

software is science too.

information

Prone to breaking due to dependencies and evolving environments

both can be digital objects

Must be described!

Software is often the best explanation for data results (when data is generated computationally)

Both should state provenance and descriptive metadata

Iterative accumulation

What do data and software have in common?

Software is a special type of data

What makes data and software different?

Object vs process

Software is executable, data is not

Level of complexity

Data is static, software is procedure

Software is a special type of data

software is executable

software needs to be maintained
(evolving OS environments)

Software is executable (can be run
with multiple parameters, multiple
times). Data states facts

software is executable

What makes data and software different?

Software changes more frequently than data

Written by humans vs. generated

Software implements a process, data captures characteristics of things

Data is passive

People think that data can only be right or wrong, whereas software is on a spectrum.

Software is executable, which adds extra complications to the data nature of software

copyright

you need software to process data but not vice versa

What is the relationship between software and code?

Code makes software

Software acts on data - collects, manipulates, creates

if software is a set, code is its subset

Software is the entity that is represented by the code. You can have multiple code bases for the same software

code is the knowledge representation of software. it is human readable.

Code is a form of software, software is broader

Code are the instructions, software is the thing you interact with

Like the human body compared to the sum of its cells

code as the static part, software as the executable counterpart

What is the relationship between software and code?

code is a materialization of the software

software represents a use. Code the approach to it

no, because you can have a well-described software whose metadata is accessible, but need an agreement/license to access it, use it

Software is
(not) data

Software is
(not) data

vs.

Research Software

Research software is software on which research results depend.

Many forms.

Many purposes.

Many distribution channels.

Traditionally, often created as Free and Open Source Software (FOSS).

FAIR and FOSS

Clear overlap of objectives, but not the same.

FOSS: Open source code, open licenses.

FAIR: Open data not a requirement.

Due to, e.g., privacy and sensitivity concerns with patients' health records.

Not in the same way valid for research software.

There is even a demand to make methods available!

Should FAIR software require FOSS?

Ongoing discussion ...

What do you think? Should FAIR require software to have an open license? Why, or why not?

Ideally so, because they form part of the publically available research output

yes, or the default should be open because the knowledge of the research is in the source code

Yes, to improve reproducibility

No, FAIR does not imply open. It can be closed and still FAIR.

Yes, because it significantly boosts the F, the A and the I.

Should require, with some potential exceptions (e.g. related to confidentiality of personal information, other legislation)

I would recommended because we are doing this so software is findable; but I would not require it.

No. Research software produced in research facilities of enterprises may be closed.

No -- as long as there is a license it is FAIR enough

What do you think? Should FAIR require software to have an open license? Why, or why not?

not always: if the testsuite relies on sensitive data, the code will be made public without that data, and the testsuite will not pass

No, following the A1.2 principle we can have restricted/protected data, like some case of softwares

No, FAIRness is about the description of the research object, but the conditions to access it don't need to be open

Only required if financed with public funds

Yes, or at least by default. The research knowledge is in the source code

yes, there are tools to automate improving code quality, and tools to plot your GitHub project quality vs. others

no. sometimes software is developed in a partnership that dictates license conditions.

Unsure. Depends on the extent of reproducible software

FAIR and software quality

Software quality is a major concern in RSE.

Can FAIR meet the expectations?

Distinguish between **form** and **function** of software:

Quality of the **form** of software can be covered by FAIR (code quality, maintainability).

Quality of the **functionality** of software goes beyond FAIR (functional correctness, software security, computational efficiency).

Should FAIR also take content quality into account?

Why (not)?

No. Bad data is good data

No. Quality is quite subjective (what is not usable in one community may be useful in others)

no, but principles about software should include quality

No, code review should be part of a publication process and not for all research software

Yes, but only as part of Reusability - and here it should only be "does it do what it does it says on the tin" as quality is subjective.

Reusability part of FAIR implies quality of data so why not same for software?

Not, quality is relative

Quality of the form is essential for FAIR, not the quality of the functionality

No, quality is too complex and can vary a lot (e.g., across communities), it can also be subjective

Should FAIR also take content quality into account?

Why (not)?

some aspects of interoperability relate to quality

Functional correctness seems vital for interoperability and reproducibility

Yes -- for reusability it is necessary to have a minimum level of quality which allows others to run the software (e.g. a README file)

Would be good but subjective (to produce good quality research you need good quality data or software but it's up to users what they decide to use/reuse in the end)

FAIR Software Reading List

Towards FAIR principles for research software
<https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-190026>

FAIRsFAIR report on FAIRness of software
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4095092>

RDA FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) WG
<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-research-software-fair4rs-wg>

Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555497>

Five Recommendations for FAIR Software
<https://fair-software.eu>

Five Recommendations for FAIR Software

1. Use a publicly accessible repository with version control.
2. Add a license.
3. Register your code in a community registry.
4. Enable citation of the software.
5. Use a software quality checklist.

How about your software? Do you...

break

What 2021 events would be a good location for FAIR4RS principles consultation?

What organisations or events would like to work with us to enable consultation in your community?

What types of materials would be helpful to facilitate discussions about FAIR 4 Research Software?

